

Author: *Chiara Tea Antoniazzi – WP6*
(last updated January 2026)

Report on Climate-Related Litigation and the Separation of Powers

D 7.6 tasks 7-8 WP7 D2.2. tasks 7-8 Wp2
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.19733770

The mounting wave of climate-related litigation has led to growing discussions on the role of the principle of the separation of powers. The issue has been addressed in several scholarly works, and it has also been raised by defendant governments and referred to by judges in their decisions. The crux of the matter is whether and to what extent courts should be able to question legislation approved by parliaments and enacted by governments with democratic legitimacy.¹ According to certain views, courts should be particularly cautious in an area of especially complex policy, in relation to which legislative and executive bodies have a wide range of courses of action among which to choose; moreover, these political bodies can take into consideration and balance a broader spectrum of interests, including by allowing public participation and incorporating scientific expertise.² On the other hand, it is argued that the involvement of judges through climate litigation is warranted by their core functions of keeping the other branches within the limits of the law and of enforcing rights.³

¹ On the challenges to (and opportunities for) democracy presented by climate litigation, see Michele Poletto & Sharon Pia Hickey (eds.), *LET THE COURTS DECIDE? THE POTENTIAL AND LIMITATIONS OF CLIMATE LITIGATION FROM A DEMOCRACY PERSPECTIVE* (2025).

² For an oft-cited radical criticism of climate litigation, see Phil Goldberg, *Climate change lawsuits are ineffective political stunts*, THE HILL, 1 March 2018, <<https://thehill.com/opinion/energy-environment/376307-climate-change-lawsuits-are-showy-ineffective-political-stunts/>>.

³ Ivano Alogna, Natalie K. Arnould & Alina Holzhausen, *The Role of Judges in Implementing Climate Policies*

The practice of courts in deciding climate-related cases and in addressing arguments concerning the separation of powers varies considerably. The *Leghari* case, decided by the Lahore High Court in 2015, stands out as a decision where the court went into great detail in its orders to the executive – by *inter alia* instructing the appointment of “climate change focal persons” within relevant ministries, the presentation of a list of action points in the area of climate change adaptation, and the institution of a “climate change commission” with a view to assisting the court in monitoring the implementation of the decision. In the *Urgenda* case, the Dutch Supreme Court (December 2019) ordered the government to reduce emissions by a specific amount. As such, it has been criticised by some as a (negative) example of judicial activism or over-reaching,⁴ even though ample freedom was left to the Dutch government in deciding how to reach the emission reduction target imposed by the Supreme Court. A similar approach was followed in the Belgian *VZW Klimaatzaak* case, although in this instance the Court of Appeal referred to a target which had already been enshrined in EU law.⁵

In other cases, the legislative and executive branches were left with an even wider margin of appreciation and courts have refrained from any specific indication as regards both the *quantum* and the modalities of emissions reduction. This is the case, among others, of *Klimaseniorinnen and Others v. Switzerland*, decided by the European Court of Human Rights on 9 April 2024. According to the Court (para. 412),

[j]udicial intervention ... cannot replace or provide any substitute for the action which must be taken by the legislative and executive branches of government. However, democracy cannot be reduced to the will of the majority of the electorate and elected representatives, in disregard of the requirements of the rule of law. The remit of domestic courts and the Court is therefore complementary to those democratic processes. The task of the judiciary is to ensure the necessary oversight of compliance with legal requirements.

In light of this, while the Court found that Switzerland had violated Article 8 of the European Convention on Human Rights by, among others, omitting to set up an appropriate domestic regulatory framework and to quantify GHG emissions reduction targets, it did not set targets nor order the adoption of specific measures by the Swiss government, instead highlighting that “having regard to the complexity and the nature of the issues involved, the Court is unable to be detailed or prescriptive as regards any measures to be implemented in order to effectively comply with the present judgment” (para. 657).

While some regard any decision by a court on climate policy as an unacceptable interference with the legislative and executive mandates, it is difficult to consider these judgments a violation of the separation of powers.⁶ Nonetheless, various courts refused to adjudicate applications on the merits because the issues raised were qualified as essentially political and thus within the purview of the executive branch (in accordance with the so-called

A Comparative Perspective on the Separation of Powers, in IMPLEMENTING CLIMATE CHANGE POLICY: DESIGNING AND DEPLOYING NET ZERO CARBON GOVERNANCE 271, 274 (Ottavio Quirico & Walter Baber eds., 2024).

⁴ See, for an overview of the criticisms concerning an alleged violation of the separation of powers, K. J. de Graaf & J. H. Jans, *The Urgenda Decision: Netherlands Liable for Role in Causing Dangerous Global Climate Change*, 27 JOURNAL OF ENVIRONMENTAL LAW 517, 523-525 (2015).

⁵ See paras. 282 ff. See also para. 227, where the Court of Appeal draws the line between permissible and impermissible judicial action in the context of the separation of powers.

⁶ See, in support, Christina Eckes, *Separation of Powers in Climate Cases: Comparing cases in Germany and the Netherlands*, VERFASSUNGSBLOG, 10 May 2021, <<https://verfassungsblog.de/separation-of-powers-in-climate-cases/>>.

political question doctrine). Exemplary of this trend are the so-called *Aurora* case in Sweden;⁷ the *A Sud et al.* case in Italy;⁸ the so-called *People v. Arctic Oil* case in Norway;⁹ and the *La Rose et al.* case in Canada.¹⁰ The issue has also featured prominently in several cases before courts in the United States, such as in the *Juliana* case, although the failure of the legal proceedings ultimately hinged on the lack of standing of the applicants (which was not, in any case, unrelated to the issues of separation of powers and non-justiciability of claims).¹¹

The above-mentioned case-law demonstrates how the principle of the separation of powers is not interpreted homogeneously in all countries and thus leads to different results.¹²

What are the observed and expected impacts of these trends on the use of HRJs by States in the context of climate litigation? Firstly, depending on the legal system wherein the case is submitted, it might be easier for the defendant government to obtain an inadmissibility decision based on the non-justiciability of climate policy. Secondly, should a case be decided on the merits, it can be expected that courts will hear and accept HRJs (or related notions) that are crafted in general terms: for instance, in *Klimaseniorinnen*, the Swiss government confined itself to state that “[c]limate protection measures may restrict the freedoms of individuals and the most sensible solutions need to be found, after balancing all the interests involved”. Finally, courts will likely continue, in a majority of jurisdictions, to leave a wide margin of discretion to governments in modelling their response to the climate crisis. Nevertheless, it cannot be excluded that, should the inaction of governments persist and the seriousness of the threat worsen, courts might become willing to intervene more decidedly with respect to climate policy and legislation. In such a scenario, courts might scrutinise HRJs and related notions more stringently.

Recommendations:

- Civil society organisations that are considering bringing climate-related proceedings should carefully examine the approach of the relevant court(s) to the principle of the separation of powers, especially in the area of climate change (if previous cases exist).
- Public authorities should monitor the evolving case-law on climate change, both at the international level and in other countries, as cross-fertilisation and judicial dialogue could have an impact on their own courts’ decisions.

⁷ Linnéa Nordlander, *Constitutional Boundaries After Verein Klimaseniorinnen: Lessons on Domestic Rights-Based Climate Change Litigation from the Swedish Supreme Court’s Aurora Judgment*, 34 REVIEW OF EUROPEAN, COMPARATIVE & INTERNATIONAL ENVIRONMENTAL LAW 566 (2025).

⁸ For some comments on the case focusing on the issue of separation of powers, see Moritz Vinken & Paolo Mazzotti, *The First Italian Climate Judgement and the Separation of Powers*, VERFASSUNGSBLOG, 22 April 2024, <<https://verfassungsblog.de/the-first-italian-climate-judgement-and-the-separation-of-powers/>>; and Umberto Lattanzi, *Climate Litigation Reaches Italian Courts: Giudizio Universale*, VERFASSUNGSBLOG, 12 April 2024, <<https://verfassungsblog.de/climate-litigation-reaches-italian-courts/>>.

⁹ On the scope of judicial review as outlined by the Norwegian Supreme Court, see Christina Voigt, *The First Climate Judgment before the Norwegian Supreme Court: Aligning Law with Politics*, 33 JOURNAL OF ENVIRONMENTAL LAW 697, 706-708 in particular (2021).

¹⁰ According to the Federal Court, “the diffuse nature of the claim that targets all conduct leading to GHG emissions cannot be characterized in a way other than to suggest the Plaintiffs’ are seeking judicial involvement in Canada’s overall policy response to climate change” (*La Rose v. His Majesty the King*, 2020 FC 1008 (Federal Court, 27 October 2020), para. 44). The case is currently under appeal.

¹¹ See *Juliana v. United States. Ninth Circuit Holds that Developing and Supervising Plan to Mitigate Anthropogenic Climate Change Would Exceed Remedial Powers of Article III Court*, 134 HARVARD LAW REVIEW 1929 (2021). For other US cases where the political question doctrine arose, see UNEP, *Climate Change in the Courtroom: Trends, Impacts and Emerging Lessons* (2025).

¹² Heather Colby, Ana Stella Ebbersmeyer, Lisa Marie Heim & Marthe Kielland Røssaak, *Judging Climate Change: The Role of the Judiciary in the Fight Against Climate Change*, 7(3) OSLO LAW REVIEW 168 (2020).

